

INCIDENCE OF AV BLOCK IN INFERIOR STEMI

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Abstract

Background: Atrioventricular (AV) block is an AV conduction disorder that can manifest in various settings, with varying symptomatology and severity. Complications of acute ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) as AV blocks are often observed.

Methodology: All newly diagnosed inferior wall MI patients were included to conducted in French Medical Institute for children and mother (FMIC) from 1st January 2023 to December 2023. Prior ethical clearance from the Institutional Ethics Committee was taken. Written informed consent was taken from the study participants. Detailed history, physical examination, and necessary investigations were done in all patients. Electrocardiographic (ECG) were recorded on admission and everyday thereafter till hospital discharge. AV block was evaluated. All this information was recorded on Performa for analysis.

Results: Overall there were 40 registered patients of Inferior wall STEMI cases, of which 32 (80%) were men and 8 (20%) women. Sex ratio was 4 (male to female) based on the revealed ratio of Inferior wall ST elevation Myocardial infarction are more common in males than females. The age of patients varied between 39 to 85 years. We revealed that the mean and median ages of patients diagnosed with inferior wall ST elevation Myocardial infarction were 58.1 and 59.0 years respectively. Most of cases were seen at 60 years. When the age range based on gender was analyzed, it turned out that the age range for males varied between 39-85 with mean age of 58.13 years, whereas in female the age varied between 48-85 years with a mean range 59 years. We analyzed the Presentation of patient in emergency department 30 patients (75%) came in acute stage and 10 patients (25%) came in late stage. Regarding to involvement the coronary arteries, RCA (Right coronary artery) is more effected 27 patients (67.5%), LCX (left circumflex artery) 7 patient (17.5%) and 4 patients (10%) by LAD (left

anterior ascending artery). For 2 patients (5%) angiography was not done due to financial problem. The most common involved coronary is RCA. This involvement shows by angiography. Patients presented in emergency department for treatment, 30 patients (75%) in acute stage and 10 (25%) present in late stage. In acute presentation for 19 patients (47.5%) primary PCI done, for 5 patients (12.5%) thrombolysis and PCI done, for 2 pats (5%) give atropine-apply TPM and Primary PCI done, 1 patient (2.5%) advised CABG, 1 patient (2.5%) just response with atropine, 1 patient (2.5%) just thrombolysis and 1 patient (2.5%) give atropine and urgent PCI done. In late presentation for 9 patients (22.5%) PCI done and 1 patient (2.5%) thrombolysis and PCI done. In total 40 patients in both presentation (acute and late) for 19 patients (47.5%) PPCI done, PCI for 9 patients (22.5%), 6 patients (15%) thrombolysis done than PCI, for 2 pats (5%) give atropine-apply TPM and Primary PCI done, 1 patient (2.5%) advised CABG, 1 patient (2.5%) just response with atropine, 1 patient (2.5%) just thrombolysis and 1 patient (2.5%) give atropine and urgent PCI done.

Conclusion: Findings of our study were similar to data presented in other parts of the world, with some significant differences that could be explained to be related to the local factors.

INTRODUCTION

This chapter provides background information regarding incidence of AV block in Inferior STEMI epidemiology among adult myocardial infarction patients. Later part of the chapter states rationale, objectives and research questions of the study.

Background:

Any kind of irreversible damage to the cardiac muscles due to the lack of oxygen is termed 'myocardial infarction'. Myocardial infarction is often thought as a sudden or unexpected conditions, however, this is not true. There are several insults and damages taking place inside the heart silently, and only when irreversible or non-treatable changes have taken place inside the heart then is the time when the person complaints of the presenting symptoms or complaints of a developing myocardial infarction. The prevalence of acute myocardial infarction seems to be increasing with time. It is estimated that approximately one million deaths in the United State occur annually due to these events of unexpected and acute MI. Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) represents clinically by unstable angina pectoris, non-ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI), or STEMI. It is related to life-threatening complications. [1] The symptoms of MI vary from patient to patient, with many of them appearing with only mild ones such as

chest pain and restlessness. Others may complaint of severe jaw, arm, or hand pain that does not seem to stop at all. In all such conditions, an ECG should be ordered immediately. An ECG also helps in excluding any other related cause that might be causing these symptoms. Arrhythmias are common, potentially lethal, and treatable complications of ACS. Such arrhythmias are usually transient and typically resolve within 24 h. However, it is vital to recognize and initiate necessary treatment early as they can progress to irreversible and lethal disturbances. Atrioventricular (AV) block is an AV conduction disorder that can manifest in various settings, with varying symptomatology and severity. Complications of acute ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) as AV blocks are often observed [1].

To understand the conduction disorders in AMI setting, knowledge of vascular supply of the conduction system of the heart is very important. Sinoatrial Node is supplied by the Sinonodal Artery which arises from Right Coronary Artery (RCA) in 2/3rd cases and from Left Circumflex artery (LCx) in rest of the cases. Atrioventricular node again gets its blood supply from the RCA in majority of cases, and rest through LCx. Right Bundle Branch and the Anterior Fascicle of Left Bundle Branch receive their blood supply from LAD, while the post fascicle of left bundle branch has dual blood supply both from

RCA and LAD [9]. Therefore, atrioventricular block (AVB) is more frequent in inferior STEMI, which is usually related to RCA occlusion. Ischemia of the conduction system can cause Brady arrhythmias. [5] Even after ACS, necrotic changes in the sinoatrial node can cause sinus arrest. Sinus bradycardia occurs in 15–25% of patients with ACS. Patients with ACS associated persistent or hemodynamic instability bradyarrhythmias warrant consideration of temporary ventricular pacing (TVP). A permanent pacemaker is not typically necessary for bradyarrhythmias following ACS because bradyarrhythmias are transient in most cases. [8] Several days of the observation period were suitable for a permanent pacemaker decision. AVB associated with ACS is frequent, numerous in types, and associated with poor prognosis. [10,11].

The most significant AVB after ACS is high-degree AVB (2nd-degree Type 2 and 3rd-degree) and intraventricular conduction defects. [12] In studies, the complete AVB (CAVB) incidence with inferior STEMI was 7.3–13% and with anterior STEMI was 3.6–4.9%. [13,16] Studies have shown that STEMI patients with conduction disorders have a poor in-hospital prognosis. [3] However, the long-term impact of conduction abnormalities among ACS patients is unclear. *The first degree of atrioventricular block is the most common and requires no treatment. The second-degree block is sub-classified in Mobitz type I and Mobitz type II [1,2].* “Complete heart block, also called third-degree heart block, is a condition in which no signals can pass from atria to ventricles.” It is relatively uncommon and is regarded as the most serious heart block. Common causes of this pathological condition include coronary ischemia leading to progressive degeneration of the conducting system of heart [3].

Significant atrioventricular (AV) block, defined as the acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is often associated with increased morbidity and mortality. Various studies have reported the incidence of significant AV block in ACS between 3% and 14% with an increased risk of in-hospital death [4, 6, 7]. Factors linked with the development of AV block in the setting of STEMI include: hypertension, diabetes mellitus, smoking, older age, female gender, prior myocardial infarction and presence of multi vessel coronary artery disease [7]. The mortality rate of an

inferior wall MI is less than 10%. However, several complicating factors that increase mortality, including right ventricular infarction, hypotension, bradycardia heart block, and cardiogenic shock. Prognosis of ST segment elevation myocardial infarction patients developing these complications is poor. [10,11,12,13]. Complication and mortality rates of ST segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) markedly declined over the past 20 years owing to widespread use of reperfusion therapies, modern antithrombotic treatments and recommended prevention drugs. High degree atrioventricular block (HAVB) is a common complication of STEMI that is reported in 2.7% to 14% of patients. Similarly, to other complications, rate of AV block has been shown to be decreasing over time, However the presence of AV block in the acute phase of STEMI is known to be associated with an increased in hospital mortality regardless of reperfusion therapy. Primary percutaneous coronary intervention (p-PCI) especially when performed in a timely fashion, is currently the treatment of choice of STEMI.

The type and severity of atrioventricular (AV) block associated with COVID-19 have not been described. We aimed to evaluate the incidence of the AV block as a complication, angiographic findings, and clinical outcome in the setting of acute inferior STEMI in patients with COVID-19 infection. We noted that the incidence of atrioventricular block as one of the complications of acute inferior STEMI is higher in patients who were tested as COVID-19 positive versus COVID-19 negative cases. [8,9]. vagal tone as a paradoxical cause of coronary artery spasm, coinciding with complete heart block. It will additionally identify proper management in these cases. [14].

All that matters is whether the patient could be saved or not. Only early, immediate, and prompt treatment and therapeutic interventions could help assure the fact regarding the survival of the patient. Percutaneous Intervention and Follow-up for these patients were coronary angiographic view suggests the culprit’s vessel. The therapeutic approach was based on coronary angiograms for all patients. Moreover, coronary angioplasty was performed after the angiogram. Moreover, the pacing procedure was performed according to the guidelines. [17-19] TVP was inserted, followed for several days, and removed before discharge

from the hospital if the rhythm recovered. Implantation of permanent pacemaker and ICD after AVB is rare and remains controversial. In the majority of cases, AVB resumes rapidly. If the bradyarrhythmia does not disappear after 1–3 weeks of hospitalization advanced interventional methods (permanent pacemaker or ICD) are tried. It is estimated that any treatment that is begun within six hours after the onset of symptoms can help treat the patient effectively and appropriately. (7) However, as easy as they might appear to be when treated, complications such as proper right ventricular involvement occur because of the various cases of inferior wall MI. Such difficulties further complicate the patient's condition and lead to further serious consequences such as heart block. (8)

However, it is time management protocols such as the beginning of percutaneous coronary intervention that promptly causes the patient's life to be saved in due time. The rest of the protocol also depends on the skills of the person providing this treatment, but usually the effects of percutaneous coronary intervention can be observed immediately after it has been started. According to guidelines opening of an infarct related artery in late presenter (48hr) is of no benefit and nothing is mentioned about reperfusion therapy in case of Inferior wall MI complicated by Complete Heart block as a late presenter. (9) The main goal of reperfusion therapy is to save the life of the patient and reverse as much damage as could be easily reversed by establishing blood flow to the myocardium. Knowing that it is important as it would help improve the mortality and morbidity rates associated with acute myocardial infarction in different hospital settings. This study will also work as a guide to direct the appropriate interventions, such as percutaneous coronary interventions(PCI) for saving the life of a patient as soon as they are brought to the emergency department with inferior wall MI complicated by CHB as a late presenter. The objective of this study was to evaluate the outcomes of delayed presenters with acute inferior wall MI complicated by complete heart block treated by PCI of culprit artery.

It was found that almost all of the patients who received primary PCI after their acute MI attack were successfully treated and recovered spontaneously. This was discovered after comparing different MI patients. All groups of patients were simultaneously treated with thrombolysis and PCI to see which treatment protocol yielded the most favorable results. It was concluded that

these patients with complete atrioventricular(AV) blocks were found to have such a favorable outcome when treated with PCI that it was finally realized that it is indeed a necessary protocol that should be added to the priority-based management of myocardial infarction for all patients and not just the ones suffering from inferior wall MIs. (18). All in all, percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) was found to safely ameliorate conditions like inferior wall MI from further complicating the condition of the patient.

Rationale:

FMIC, Department of Cardiology is one of the leading tertiary health care centers in country that receive patients from all over the country and routinely All cardiac procedure done here including ECG, TTE, TEE, ETT, Angiography, Angioplasty, TPM, PPM & EPS with RFA. Thus, we claim that our study will be well-qualified to represent the prevalence of AV blocks in STEMI patients and treatment on time to decrease the morbidity and mortality in Afghanistan. To our best knowledge, this is going to be the first study ever done on Blocks patient among Inferior wall STEMI in Afghanistan. Our study will not only help to provide a reliable platform for further studies in this section, but also a good source of information to build successful PCI of culprit artery even in late presenter of CHB with acute inferior MI results in restoration of NSR in all patients with reduction in heart block recovery time and no in hospital death.

Research Objectives:

- To study various patterns of conduction blocks occurring in ST elevation myocardial infarction.
- To study the prognostic implications of conduction blocks occurring in ST elevation myocardial infarction.
- To study the relation of conduction blocks with ST elevation Myocardial Infarction and implementing it to detect morbidity or mortality associated with it.

Research Questions:

- What is the frequency of STEMI and blocks by age and gender of patients diagnosed in a tertiary care setting in Afghanistan?
- What is the presentation (Acute or Late) and PPCI done or not?
- Which Heart block is common in an Inferior wall STEMI?

- Which Coronary artery is more involved in an Inferior wall STEMI?
- What are the common treatment techniques applied for blocks and Inferior wall STEMI?
- What is the patient outcome after treatment?

Summary of the Chapter

In brief, the chapter explained the nature of blocks in STEMI, including its definition, epidemiology and some important characteristics and elaborated upon the data available in literature. Finally, the rationale of the study was explained that defines the impact of our study on the national health care system, followed by clear research objectives and research questions.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

The literature has been flooded with studies conducted across the world indicating the prevalence of AV block in Acute Inferior ST- segment elevation myocardial infarction patients. It includes review of global and regional studies related to this topic. To the best of my knowledge, this is the first study regarding spectrum of findings after treatment and outcomes of patients in Afghanistan.

Search Strategy:

Several “online datasets and search instruments like Pub Med, Google Scholar and Henari databases using to search the papers for the research questions related “to Ischemic heart disease (IHD), AV Blocks, Inferior Wall ST elevation MI and percutaneous coronary intervention(PCI). The study on national, regional and global level were included comprising both the developed and developing countries. The majority of related recently published studies in English language were reviewed and included.

Literature:

Several studies have been described in the literature highlighting the age, gender, onset, Types of blocks and treatment strategy.

In a study of 311 patients by **DAR, W. A., et al** using age 40 and above were included in this study, of which 31.5% were in the age group of 40-50 years, while the rest of 68.5% were in the age group of ≥ 51 years with an overall mean age of 55.6 ± 8.4 years. Gender distribution of patients shows a higher

frequency of 57.9% males compared to 42.1% females, with female to male ratio of 1:1.4. Distribution of patients with reference to the high degree of atrioventricular block was found to be present among 5.8% of the total recruited cases (2).

In another study conducted by **SAVIĆ, Lidija, et al** using 3044 consecutive STEMI Patients just 144 patients registered Complete AV block only an admission (4.73%). 125 patients with complete AV block had Inferior infarction. 72 patients need to implanted Temporary pacemaker, no patients underwent to permanent pacemaker implantation. In hospital mortality (IHM) significantly higher in patients with complete AV block than in patients without complete AV blocks: 17.9% vs. 3.6% (4).

A study done in **Pakistan** by **ULLAH, Zia, et al** the number of patients 233 and the patients mean age was 62 ± 8.04 year. Enrolled males were 59% while females were 41% in this study. Results showed that 19% patients had complete heart block while 81% were without it (5).

In **North-Eastern India** study done by **DUTTA, Bornali, et al** study population was divided into case and control groups based on the presence of significant AV block, either at admission or during hospitalization. A total of 1001 patients with ACS were included. One hundred and twenty-five patients of ACS with significant AV block comprised the study population (cases) and the rest 876 patients with ACS without significant AV block comprised the control population. The overall incidence of significant AV block was 12.48%. Percentage of patients undergoing temporary pacemaker implantation or percutaneous coronary intervention during hospitalization was higher in cases. At 30 days, mortality was significantly higher among cases (24% vs. 8.1%) (6).

In an analytic study done by **YOUSIF, Akram, et al**, this study was conducted at the National Institute of Cardiovascular Diseases (NICVD), **Karachi**. They enrolled 165 patients with acute inferior STEMI who presented with any degree of AV block. All patients received PPCI as an initial therapeutic strategy. Out of 165 enrolled patients, AV block was more common in the older patients (mean age 60.08 ± 10.09 years), in males 118 (71.5%), and in 86 (52.1%) patients with multi vessel coronary artery disease. The predominant culprit artery was the right

coronary artery in 152 (92.1%) patients. 139 (84.2%) patients had restoration of normal AV conduction at end of 5 days of hospitalization. The average time for reversal of AV block was 51.3 ± 30.2 hours. 23 (14%) patients had persistent AV block and underwent permanent pacemaker implantation. 3 (1.8%) patients had in-hospital mortality (7).

In their study of **S B Gupta** found that the conduction disorders are frequently associated with Inferior wall ST elevation MI. Usually, the conduction disorders associated with STEMI are transient and benign and are reversible with reperfusion therapy. Temporary pacing is indicated if there is hemodynamic compromise and/or High degree AVB in acute AAMI setting (9).

Gap Analysis:

The literature review showed significant benefit of early percutaneous coronary intervention reduced mortality rate, improved the recovery of patient and that PPCI is the best choice over thrombolytic if feasible. Unfortunately, no study was found which reported about the recovery of patient from blocks after PPCI in the patient population within Afghanistan. Considering the lack of studies related to epidemics of “prevalence of AV blocks in Inferior ST elevation MI and rate of recovery from blocks after Primary PCI” patient’s in Afghanistan, our study can answer the study question to some extent and can provide a platform upon which further large and nationwide studies can be carried out which will help fill the gap in this regard.

Chapter Summary:

To summarize, this chapter explained the various results achieved by different studies carried out and published in the international medical journals regarding the prevalence, Onset, types of AV blocks, as well as, the common techniques used for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes. The studies reviewed regionally and globally provide the information about our study from existing literatures. Gap analysis showed absence of such studies in Afghanistan.

Chapter Three: Methodology

In this chapter, the research method applied for the investigation of disease, types of AV blocks, clinical

information and other related materials are described. The chapter includes; study design, study setting, study participants, eligibility criteria, sample method, sample size, study period, data collection period, data collection method, variables of interest, data management, data analysis plan and ethical consideration of our study.

All newly diagnosed inferior wall MI patients were included to conducted in French Medical Institute for children and mother (FMIC) from 1st January 2023 to December 2023. Prior ethical clearance from the Institutional Ethics Committee was taken. Written informed consent was taken from the study participants. Detailed history, physical examination, and necessary investigations were done in all patients. Electrocardiographic (ECG) were recorded on admission and everyday thereafter till hospital discharge. AV block was evaluated. All this information was recorded on Performa for analysis.

Study Design:

Cross-sectional (Prevalence) study.

Study Setting:

The tertiary-level hospital of French medical institute for Children and Mothers (FMIC), is a 169 bedded hospital based in Kabul, Afghanistan founded in 2006. It serves approximately 1500 admissions per year including all cardiac patients and provides high quality services for inpatient, outpatient, SDU, CCU, ICU, ICCU and Emergency room referring from all over Afghanistan. All cardiac procedure done here including ECG, TTE, TEE, ETT, Angiography, Angioplasty, TPM, PPM & EPS with RFA.

Study Participants:

The study population was all AV block cases who have Inferior STEMI, either at admission or during hospitalization. The baseline clinical characteristics, which were analyzed (type of AV block), Mode of presentation, clinical course in the hospital, treatment in hospital and prognosis.

Study duration:

Study duration is from 1st January 2023 to December 2023.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

1. Patients must be >18 years of age
2. Patients must fulfil the diagnostic criteria of ACS as given below: Diagnosis of myocardial infarction (MI) was made if there is: Typical rise and gradual fall (troponin) or more rapid rise and fall (CK-MB) of biochemical markers of myocardial necrosis with at least one of the following [6].
 - a. Ischemic symptoms (Typical history of chest pain presenting for > 30 min).
 - b. Classical ECG changes indicating ACUTE MI. (ST-segment elevation in Inferior leads) with AV block.
 - c. Elevated cardiac enzymes levels CK-MB and troponin I.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Patients who were initially treated elsewhere and referred to the study center only for additional management.
2. Patients with old bundle branch block.
3. Patients with cardiomyopathy.
4. Patients with congenital or Rheumatic heart disease.
5. Patients with history of intake of drugs causing conduction blocks like clonidine, methyl dopa, verapamil, digoxin etc. All the patients included in the study was explained about the procedure in detail and issued Patient Information Sheet. Informed and written consent was taken in each case.

Data collection method:

A check list is prepared to collect the data from the file of patients. All Inferior wall STEMI patient who visited FMIC from 1st January 2023 to 30 December 2023 fulfilling the inclusion criteria will be included in the study.

Simple Method and size:

All Inferior wall STEMI patient who visited FMIC from 1st January 2023 to 30 December 2023 fulfilling the inclusion criteria will be included in the study.

Variables of Interest:

AV block patient with complication, treatment and prognosis.

Data management:

The principle investigator will collect the data and save it in both soft and hard copies of well designated data collection forms in Microsoft Excel worksheets. Soft copies will be kept secured with a key-password in a reliable database and the hard copies will be kept protected with the principle investigator.

• Data Entry:

The data will be entered and analyzed twice to minimize the errors and afterwards data will be screened and edited.

• Pre-testing

Validity and reliability of data collection tools: in order to evaluate the internal validity and reliability of the data collection instrument ten independent experts rated each item of the questionnaires on questions' relevancy and clarity. Internal validity index was calculated based on the rating done by the expert and was obtained to be 96%. For reliability, the data obtained by rating were entered into SPSS software and Cronbach Alpha was calculated for internal consistency, the cut off for Cronbach Alpha was 88%.

Analysis plan:

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) application, version 25, will be used for data analysis.

Descriptive Statistical Analysis Plan: Considering the type of data, Frequency and Proportions will be used for calculating Categorical Variables, while Mean, Median, Mode and Standard Deviation (SD) will be used to describe Continuous Variables. The Mean will be calculated if the data is symmetrically distributed and the median will be run for skewed distribution.

Ethical Consideration:

After developing the proposal for the study, it will be sent for FMIC ERC and afterwards, Ministry of Public Health PGME ERC approval. By receiving

their approval, we will start the data collection. A checklist is developed to collect the data from medical records of patients. MR number of patients will be used to gather the data. Identification of patients will not be disclosed in any manner. We will keep the soft copy of data in an encrypted file in personal laptop and the hard copy of data in a locked key box. Only the principal investigator will have the authorization over the primary data.

Dissemination:

The results of the study will be shared in hard copies with the Ministry of Public Health, Ministry of Higher Education, Kabul University of Medical Sciences (KUMS) “Abu Ali Ibn Sina”, FMIC and other academic institutions at Kabul, Afghanistan. It will be uploaded online at FMIC and Aga Khan University websites. I am committed to present the findings of the study in different scientific seminars, academic conferences and social cancer awareness gatherings inside and outside the country as well as I

will be willing to publish it in one of the international peer-reviewed medical journals.

Summary of the chapter:

A cross sectional descriptive study was conducted to achieve the objectives of the study through variables of interest in a specific population and particular period of time, at a tertiary care center in Kabul, Afghanistan. The data was collected by non-probability convenience sampling method. The analysis was done using descriptive statistics. Rules for ethical consideration were strictly followed

Chapter Four: Results

Overall there were 40 registered patients of Inferior wall STEMI cases, of which 32 (80%) were men and 8 (20%) women (Figure 1). Sex ratio was 4 (male to female) based on the revealed ratio of Inferior wall ST elevation Myocardial infarction are more common in males than females.

Figure 1: Sex distribution

The age of patients varied between 39 to 85 years. We revealed that the mean and median ages of patients diagnosed with inferior wall ST elevation Myocardial infarction were 58.1 and 59.0 years respectively. Most of cases were seen at 60 years

(Figure 2). When the age range based on gender was analyzed, it turned out that the age range for males varied between 39-85 with mean age of 58.13 years, whereas in female the age varied between 48-85 years with a mean range 59 years (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Age distribution

Figure 3: Age distribution related to gender

We analyzed the Presentation of patient in emergency department 30 patients (75%) came in acute stage and 10 patients (25%) came in late stage. (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Presentation

Regarding to involvement the coronary arteries, RCA (Right coronary artery) is more effected 27 patients (67.5%), LCX (left circumflex artery) 7 patient (17.5%) and 4 patients (10%) by LAD (left anterior ascending artery). For 2 patients (5%) angiography was not done due to financial problem. The most common involved coronary is RCA. This involvement shows by angiography (Table 1).

Table 1: Show the percentage of culprit lesion in coronaries

L	Frequency	Percent
LAD	4	10.0
LCX	7	17.5
RCA	27	67.5
No Angiography	2	5.0
Total	40	100.0

We further analyzed the types of blocks during the attack of inferior wall ST elevation MI 26 patients (65%) were not any blocks, 11 (27.5%) patients were first degree block and 3 patients (7.5%) were third degree block.

Figure 5: Types of Blocks

Among 40 patients of inferior wall STEMI included the study we analyzed the number of patients and their percentages for various treatment stated done for patients.

Table 2: Show the percentage of treatment

	Frequency	Percent
Thrombolysis with SK	1	2.5
CABG	1	2.5
Atropine and urgent PCI	1	2.5
Atropine	1	2.5
PPCI	19	47.5
Atropine, transcutaneous temporary pacing, and PPCI	2	5.0
PCI	9	22.5

Thrombolysis + PCI	6	15.0
Total	40	100.0

Figure 6: Distribution of treatments across type of presentation

Figure 7: Distribution of treatments

Patients presented in emergency department for treatment ,30 patients (75%) in acute stage and 10 (25%) present in late stage. In acute presentation for 19 patients (47.5%) primary PCI done, for 5 patients (12.5%) thrombolysis and PCI done, for 2 pats (5%) give atropine-apply TPM and Primary PCI done, 1 patient (2.5%) advised CABG,1 patient (2.5%) just response with atropine,1 patient (2.5%) just

thrombolysis and 1 patient (2.5%) give atropine and urgent PCI done. In late presentation for 9 patients (22.5%)PCI done and 1 patient (2.5%) thrombolysis and PCI done. In total 40 patients in both presentation (acute and late) for 19 patients (47.5%) PPCI done, PCI for 9 patients (22.5%), 6 patients (15%) thrombolysis done than PCI, for 2 pats (5%) give atropine-apply TPM and Primary PCI done, 1

patient (2.5%) advised CABG, 1 patient (2.5%) just response with atropine, 1 patient (2.5%) just thrombolysis and 1 patient (2.5%) give atropine and urgent PCI done.

The last analyzed about the outcome of patients, 39 patients 97.5% was recovered and 1 patient (2.5%) was died.

Figure 8: Distribution of Outcomes

Chapter Five: Discussion

This chapter discusses the proportion and frequency of Inferior ST elevation myocardial infarction with a different type of Atrioventricular(AV) Blocks with a gender wise and age wise approach and compared it to other studies which are included in our review articles and are the latest published articles based on comprehensive studies conducted elsewhere in the world. The chapter includes the comparison between the results of our study and the findings of published studies in international literature about common types of blocks, presentation in emergency department, different approaches of treatment and effect of these treatment to outcomes. The chapter also elaborates upon the strengths and limitation of our study and the hypothesis generated for Inferior ST elevation myocardial infarction. At the end will mention the recommendation for cardiologist, critical care unites and staff, for overall health care workers regarding the treatment of STEMI, PCI and improvement of patients.

Gender Proportion and distribution:

In our study over all we had found more male (80%) cases than female (20%).when comparing with other studies, Sex ratio was 4 (male to female) based on the revealed ratio of Inferior wall ST elevation

Myocardial infarction are more common in males than females. They also had less number of female patients in their study (2,5,7). In a study conducted in Lahore Pakistan the Gender distribution of patients shows a higher frequency of 57.9% males compared to 42.1% females, with female to male ratio of 1:1.4, while another study conducted in Pakistan Enrolled males were 59% while females were 41% in this study. The last study about gender distribution conducted Karachi (NICVD) in all 165 patients the males were 118 (71.5%) and 47 (28.5%) were female. All studies show the male are more common involved in inferior ST elevation myocardial infarction than female. In Afghanistan males are more likely to smoke in comparison to female, which is a trend that was also seen in the current study. Therefore, smoking could be the reason behind the significant difference in male and female ratio of occurrence. On the other, limited numbers of patients posed as a limitation therefore there is a need for further studies to be conducted regarding gender.

Age Proportion and distribution:

Findings of the study that the majority of inferior wall ST elevation myocardial infarction diagnosed in males were in between 4th and 9th decades of life,

however in females inferior wall ST elevation myocardial infarction 5th and 9th decades of life, which supports the result that were obtained by multiple previous studies in worldwide. Similarly, in our study the age of patients varied between 39 to 85 years. We revealed that the mean and median ages of patients diagnosed with inferior wall ST elevation Myocardial infarction were 58.1 and 59.0 years respectively. Most of cases were seen at 60 years.

The age range was found almost the same in other studies of the same region as well as internationally where the mean age for patients affected by inferior wall ST elevation Myocardial infarction within the range between mean age 55.6 and 62 years (2,5). In a study conducted in Lahore Pakistan the age distribution of patients shows a higher frequency of which 31.5% were in the age group of 40-50 years, while the rest of 68.5% were in the age group of ≥ 51 years with an overall mean age of 55.6 ± 8.4 years. while another study conducted in Pakistan Enrolled the number of patients 233 and the patients mean age was 62 ± 8.04 year.

Overall in the literature various studies showed that in both genders inferior wall ST elevation Myocardial infarction are more common in older ages which supports the result of our study. The expectation is that the age group of 60 years would have more cases of inferior wall ST elevation Myocardial infarction, but our findings were contradictory. One of the reason for this findings could be based on the average life expectancy. The average life expectancy in Afghanistan is 63 years therefore comparatively less cases were reported from this age group. Additionally, since Afghanistan is a developing with people not having the privilege of free healthcare. As Angiography and PCI are costly in Afghanistan and a lot of people especially old age people tend to avoid it due to cost.

Distribution of culprit lesion in coronaries:

Regarding to involvement the coronary arteries, RCA (Right coronary artery) is more effected 27 patients (67.5%), LCX (left circumflex artery) 7 patient (17.5%) and 4 patients (10%) by LAD (left anterior ascending artery). For 2 patients (5%) angiography was not done due to financial problem. The most common involved coronary is RCA. This involvement shows by angiography. while another

study show conducted in NICVD Karachi Enrolled the predominant culprit artery was the right coronary artery in 152 (92.1%) patients. Both study show the same information about culprit lesion and right coronary artery (RCA) is involve in both.

Distribution of blocks in inferior wall ST elevation MI:

We further analyzed the types of blocks during the attack of inferior wall ST elevation MI 26 patients (65%) were not any blocks, 11 (27.5%) patients were first degree block and 3 patients (7.5%) were third degree block. Comparing with other study (2,4,5,6,7,9).

In a study conducted in Lahore Pakistan Distribution of patients with reference to the high degree of atrioventricular block was found to be present among 5.8% of the total recruited cases. The other study conducted in **Belgrade emergency hospital Serbia** using 3044 consecutive STEMI Patients just 144 patients registered Complete AV block only an admission (4.73%). 125 patients with complete AV block had Inferior infarction. While another study conducted in **Pakistan** Enrolled in 233 patients showed that 19% patients had complete heart block while 81% were without it. The study related to **India** study divided into case and control groups based on the presence of significant AV block, either at admission or during hospitalization. A total of 1001 patients with ACS were included. One hundred and twenty-five patients of ACS with significant AV block comprised the study population (cases) and the rest 876 patients with ACS without significant AV block comprised the control population. The overall incidence of significant AV block was 12.48%. The study done in **NICVD Karachi** enrolled 165 patients with acute inferior STEMI who presented with any degree of AV block. Out of 165 enrolled patients, AV block was more common in the older patients (mean age 60.08 ± 10.09 years), in males 118 (71.5%), and in 86 (52.1%) patients with multi vessel coronary artery disease. The last study done in **India** found that the conduction disorders are frequently associated with Inferior wall ST elevation MI. Usually, the conduction disorders associated with STEMI are transient and benign and are reversible with

reperfusion therapy. Our findings are correlated with all above (2,4,5,6,7,9) studies.

Distribution of treatments:

The other analyzed about the treatment, Patients presented in emergency department for treatment ,30 patients (75%) in acute stage and 10 (25%) present in late stage. In acute presentation for 19 patients (47.5%) primary PCI done, for 5 patients (12.5%) thrombolysis and PCI done, for 2 pats (5%) give atropine-apply TPM and Primary PCI done, 1 patient (2.5%) advised CABG,1 patient (2.5%) just response with atropine,1 patient (2.5%) just thrombolysis and 1 patient (2.5%) give atropine and urgent PCI done. In late presentation for 9 patients (22.5%)PCI done and 1 patient (2.5%) thrombolysis and PCI done. In total 40 patients in both presentation (acute and late) for 19 patients (47.5%) PPCI done, PCI for 9 patients (22.5%), 6 patients (15%) thrombolysis done than PCI, for 2 pats (5%) give atropine-apply TPM and Primary PCI done, 1 patient (2.5%) advised CABG,1 patient (2.5%) just response with atropine,1 patient (2.5%) just thrombolysis and 1 patient (2.5%) give atropine and urgent PCI done. Our findings correspond with SAVIĆ, Lidija, et al (4), DUTTA, Bornali, et al (6), YOUSIF, Akram, et al, (7), and S B Gupta (9).

Distribution of Outcomes:

The last analyzed about the outcome of patients,39 patients 97.5% was recovered and 1 patient (2.5%) was died. The other study also shows the high mortality in third degree AV block (4,6,9). Similarly, in different studies mention in above.

Chapter Six: Conclusion

This is the first study on the primary PCI (PPCI) and PCI treatment in Inferior wall ST elevation myocardial infarction patients reported in a tertiary care center in Afghanistan concluding:

- In this study, men were affected more than women. This is commonest to other literatures, because men are highest relative risk below the 55 years and in Afghanistan and overall males are more likely to smoke in comparison to females, which is trend that was also seen in the current study. On the other hand, limited numbers of patient posed as a limitation, therefore there is a

need for further studies to be conducted regarding gender.

- Those with the highest incidence of Inferior wall ST elevation myocardial infarction were seen at 60 years. When the age range based on gender was analyzed, it turned out that the age range for males varied between 39-85 with mean age of 58.13 years, whereas in female the age varied between 48-85 years with a mean range 59 years.

- Presentation of patient in emergency department more in acute stage than late (within 6 hours after the onset of chest pain). This is contrary to other literature because they all presented in acute stage and PPCI done for all patients. Here financial problem, long distance living of afghan people, percutaneous primary intervention not capable in government hospital and treating medically in outside of hospital are the reasons.

- The right coronary artery (RCA) is more common affected coronary then the left coronaries.

- 1st degree and 3rd degree blocks were the commonest complication in inferior wall ST elevation Myocardial infarction. Its common the conduction disorders associated with STEMI are transient and benign and are reversible with reperfusion therapy.

- Treatment done as a common protocol but in our center 1st the thrombolytic treatment done the reason are financial problem of patients and they not give consent for PPCI or PCI.

- This study focused on percutaneous coronary intervention PCI to culprit coronary artery and we had a significantly good outcome and improvement was observed. Guidelines also showed priority and recommended culprit artery over non culprit artery percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) in acute ST elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) patients.

- Our study also focused in Primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PPCI) door to balloon (D2B) time within 90 minutes of patient arrival to an emergency department (ED). It was also significantly good outcome and improvement was observed.

Strengths of the study:

The study strengths are listed as follows:

- To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first study ever done for investigating the proportion and types of blocks in Inferior STEMI patients in Afghanistan, which provides a good picture of the issue.
- The study clears the path for future comprehensive and specialized studies to be carried out regarding Myocardial Infarction patients in the country.
- This is an economical study because the principle investigator collected data from medical record files by reviewing which was already available.

Limitations of the study:

The study has some marked limitations which are listed as follows:

- Although the study was carried out in one of the leading diagnostic and therapeutic private tertiary care centers in the country, the generalization of its findings over the whole population of Afghanistan is questionable.
- The simple size of our study was quite small and a study on a larger sample of patients' needs to be conducted to validate these results. As this study has been conducted in a single PCI capable center, there was still relatively small number of patients who presented with acute STEMI due to either financial problem (the price of angiography and PCI is so high in Afghanistan and no any government and free center capable for these procedures) and long distance living of afghan people. There were fewer numbers of patients because they were treated outside of the hospital and treated medically in government hospital or primarily treated at non PCI centers due to financial issues. Finally, our data represents a single center

experience there may be a potential bias towards either the presentation of patients.

Recommendation:

Based on the findings of our study, a few significant differences were noted as compared to the studies carried out elsewhere in the world that could be explained to be related to the local factors, the following recommendations are suggested:

- Further multi centric large studies to investigate the prevalence of blocks in inferior STEMI pats in our country are required.
- In addition to that, another very important finding in our study was the presentation of Myocardial patient at late stage of the disease that can be attributed to the lack of public awareness and scarcity of specialized cardiology institutions in the country.
- Our study showed good outcomes and significant improvement in inferior STEMI patients with blocks or without blocks with PPCI and PCI so PCI capable centers is very important to treat the patients as well.
- Furthermore, detailed analysis of pathology and the search for possible causes as well as the pattern occupation and culture life style differences of each disease is highly recommended in Afghanistan. This would help give a clearer picture on the prevalence and measures required to prevent them.
- We therefore propose that further studies must be conducted with special focus on the other types of blocks in inferior wall ST elevation myocardial infarction in Afghanistan. Healthcare policies need to be changed with intent to increase public awareness and to increase availability of specialized diagnostic and therapeutic facilities.

List of Abbreviations:

FMIC	French Medical Institute for mothers and children
CAD	Coronary artery disease
ETT	Exercise tolerance test
ECG	Electrocardiogram
Echo	Echocardiography
TPM	Temporary pacemaker

PPM	Permanent pacemaker
RFA	Radiofrequency ablation
EPS	Electrophysiology study
PCI	Percutaneous coronary intervention
PPCI	Primary Percutaneous coronary intervention
CABG	Coronary artery bypass grafting
Cath lab	Catheterization laboratory
AV	Atrioventricular
STEMI	ST elevated myocardial infarction
NSTEMI	Non ST elevated myocardial infarction
ACS	Acute coronary syndrome
TVP	Temporary ventricular pacing
LAD	Left anterior descending
LCx	Left circumflex
RCA	Right coronary artery
HAVB	High atrioventricular block
CHB	Complete heart block
ICD	Implantable cardioverter defibrillator
NSR	Normal sinus rhythm
TTE	Trans thoracic echo
TEE	Trans esophageal echo
CK-MB	Creatine kinase-myoglobin binding
IHD	Ischemic heart disease
ICU	Intensive care unit
CCU	Coronary care unit
WHO	World health organization
PGME	Postgraduate medical education
MoPH	Ministry of public health

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REFERENCES:

1. Braunwald cardiology 12th edition.
2. DAR, W. A., et al. FREQUENCY OF HIGH DEGREE ATRIOVENTRICULAR BLOCK IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE ANTERIOR WALL MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION. *Biological and Clinical Sciences Research Journal*, 2023, 2023.1: 308-308.
3. HASHIM, Ali Talib; MEHMOOD, Qasim; AHMAD, Shoaib. Complete Heart Block (CHB). In: *Clinical and Surgical Aspects of Congenital Heart Diseases: Text and Study Guide*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2023. p. 141-145.
4. SAVIĆ, Lidija, et al. The impact of complete atrioventricular block on in-hospital and long-term mortality in patients treated with primary percutaneous coronary intervention. *Vojnosanitetski pregled*, 2023, 00: 4-4.
5. ULLAH, Zia, et al. Frequency of Complete Heart Block in Patients with Acute Inferior Wall Myocardial Infarction. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*, 2022, 16.05: 89-89.
6. DUTTA, Bornali, et al. Incidence, predictors, and outcome of significant atrioventricular block in acute coronary syndrome— A study from major center in North-Eastern India. *Journal of Clinical and Preventive Cardiology*, 2022, 11.1: 15.
7. YOUSIF, Akram, et al. Short Term Hospital Outcome of Atrioventricular (AV) Block in the Setting of Acute Inferior Wall Myocardial Infarction (MI) Treated by Primary Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PPCI). In: *Med. Forum*. 2022. p. 50.
8. ALAHMAD, Yaser, et al. Atrioventricular Conduction Disorders as a Complication of Inferior ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction in Patients with COVID-19 Infection. *Case Reports in Cardiology*, 2022, 2022.
9. GUPTA, S. B. Conduction Disorders in Contemporary STEMI Patients. *Welcome All Delegates*, 27.
10. WARNER, Matthew J.; TIVAKARAN, Vijai S. Inferior myocardial infarction. In: *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing, 2022.
11. GOSAVI, Rohit; JOHN, Dany P.; NASHTE, Abhijeet. Cardiac Conduction Block as Delay of Cardiac Impulse in Myocardial Infarction. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 9.02: 2022.
12. BHASIN, Dinkar, et al. A Case With Inferior Wall Myocardial Infarction and Conduction Abnormalities: Addressing the Diagnostic Challenges. *Cureus*, 2022, 14.3.
13. PATIL, V. C.; MANE, U. T.; DESAI JABBAR, V. Conduction Blocks in Myocardial Infarcts in Tertiary Care.
14. TRUGLIO, Thomas S., et al. ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction With Complete Heart Block in the Setting of Vagally Mediated Coronary Vasospasm. *Circulation*, 2022, 146.Suppl_1: A10578-A10578